

- JASMIN is a Digital Research Infrastructure
- Operated by STFC on behalf of NERC
- Supporting data-intensive environmental science

DiRAC

2nd GPU eCSE Call

- Apply for funding for RSEs to work on research software development
- Must target accelerated architectures
- Any research remit, any architecture
- Can fund local RSE or you can request an ARCHER2 expert
- Closing date: 17 Sep 2024

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk/ecse/calls/>

EXCALIBUR 10

<https://excalibur.ac.uk>

HPC RSEs: what's happening at Research Computing Services

16 people (7 new faces!)

- Core team, COZL and ICCS
- You?

In the last year we delivered:

- Dawn/AIRR
 - CSD3, Wilkes3 going strong
- Training
 - ICCS summer school
 - Workshops
- Academic collaboration
 - DiRAC, VISS/VESRI, medical

DAWN

High Performance Computing at EMBL-EBI

EMBL-EBI

EMBL-EBI Introduction

EMBL-EBI is a leading global bioinformatics institute, helping researchers analyze and share large biological datasets to drive discoveries. Based in the UK, it is a non-profit organization with a diverse, international team, funded by EMBL member states.

Bioinformatics Services

Genes, genomes & variation

Proteins: sequences, families, domains & motifs

Chemical biology

Expression

Molecular & cellular structures

Pathways & systems

HPC Services

Scientific Application

HPC Workflows

User Trainings and Workshops

Data Ingestion / Processing

HPC Consultation

SLURM Job Scheduler

HPC Infrastructure

400+ Compute Nodes

20k+ Cores

60+ Nvidia GPUs

400PB Archival Storage

5PB Scratch Space

20+ Large Memory Nodes

Management Tools

Ansible for Configuration Management

CheckMK for Infrastructure Monitoring

Warewulf for Stateless Provisioning

Interactive HPC

Data Visualization closer to computational Source

Using Open OnDemand to enable iHPC Environment

Supporting over 10+ Web and GUI applications